

FORMATION OF COMMUNICATIVE LEARNING ACTIVITIES AMONG PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THE LESSONS OF THEIR NATIVE LANGUAGE

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Annotation: The State Educational Standard for Primary General Education (SES IEO) defines the relevance of the concept of "functional literacy", which is based on the ability to set and change the goals and objectives of one's activity, plan, monitor and evaluate it, interact with the teacher and peers in the educational process, act in situations of uncertainty. Sufficiently large requirements at the present stage are imposed on the formation of functional literacy of a younger student, which creates the optimal level of language and speech development for primary language education, provided by cognitive, communicative, value-semantic, informational and personal competencies.

Key words: competence, ability to learn, analysis of objects , synthesis, derivation of consequences, establishment, construction of a logical chain, proof, hypotheses and their substantiation, statement and solution of the problem, formulation of the problem, independent creation.

Naturally, it is impossible to solve this problem by means of lesson activity alone. It is necessary to use extracurricular activities for the formation of functional language literacy. The program interprets it as a personality-oriented interaction between the teacher and the child, the purpose of which is to provide the conditions for the development of the child, his formation as a person during the school years.

In this regard, we can consider the activity in the elementary school of the work of the circle-laboratory "Young linguist", which is based on educational and research activities. This activity is aimed at personal development, the acquisition of a functional skill in the study of language as a universal way of mastering reality, the activation of a personal position, when students can independently acquire new knowledge. The role of the teacher is to organize educational and research activities, create a creative atmosphere, provide motivation, initiate and implement pedagogical support for children, accompany them.

When designing the research activity of junior schoolchildren in the Russian language, the model of the following type can be considered the most acceptable:

- encountering a language problem;
- activity planning;
- collection of scientific facts on the problem;
- experimentation, practical application of the acquired language knowledge;
- conclusions based on the analysis and generalization of the obtained data;
- analysis and self-assessment of their own activities.

Let us give an example of the organization of educational and research activities in the study of phraseological units in the laboratory "Young Linguist" in the 3rd grade.

Any activity begins with a motive, which acts as an incentive to action. At the same time, students discover the limits of their own ignorance. Students face a problem that needs to be solved. The motive for the study of phraseological units was the situation when, while studying literary works in literary reading lessons and while reading at home, children encountered expressions that were incomprehensible to them. Similar expressions were heard from many adults. There were difficulties in understanding what was read or heard.

Thus, the younger schoolchildren were faced with the task of studying the expressions unfamiliar to them - phraseological units - accepted in the Russian language.

Research activity, including educational, involves the development of hypotheses. In this case, the hypothesis was as follows: having studied set expressions, understanding their meaning, one can not only better understand works of art and people around, but also enrich one's speech.

When planning educational and research activities, children would be asked to answer the questions "What do I want to know about phraseological units? and" Why do I need to know this?

Answers to the first question showed what children want to know

- meaning, meaning of widespread phraseological units;
- the history of the emergence of set expressions in the Russian language;
- the role of phraseological units in the Russian language, as well as to explore phraseological units in other languages and compare them with Russian ones.

The answer to the second question involves the practical use of acquired knowledge.

The largest part of the work on any creative or research topic is the search for information, or the collection of scientific language facts. The success of such an activity directly depends on whether the younger student is able to search for the necessary information and process it.

In this regard, the teacher has a very important task: to acquaint students with the information storage system and teach them how to quickly search for and process information. Today there are alternative sources of information: library databases, educational, scientific and fiction literature, Internet databases.

The collection of scientific facts in the study of phraseological units would be organized in the form of presenting a system of tasks to students.

Task 1. Among the expressions you have, select those that seem familiar to you, but you do not fully understand their meaning or do not understand at all.

For this task, the children would form groups of about 5 people. Each group would use their own set of phraseological units as they completed the task, exchanging cards with each other.

Thus, students would be placed in the conditions of educational cooperation, when it is necessary to share their own experience with their comrades.

Task 2. Distribute all the marked expressions among the members of the group. Find their meanings.

To complete this task, it is advisable to form small interest groups, approximately 3 people each. The work on determining the values of set expressions would be organized in a computer class using Internet resources. To do this, the addresses of sites would have been selected in advance, taking into account their safety for children. After completing the task, the children would be able to exchange the information received, reading out the expressions they liked the most.

Thus, carrying out these tasks would help expand the vocabulary of students, develop the ability to work with a dictionary, dictionary entry, develop communication skills, as well as improve the information and communication competencies of schoolchildren. As a result, small dictionaries of phraseological units would be obtained, which could then be printed out and used in the lessons of the Russian language and literary reading.

Task 3. What are phraseological units? How did they originate in Russian?

Group work again. To answer questions, they could use linguistic dictionaries, articles, encyclopedias, write out what seemed important and significant to them. To exchange the information found and discuss the information received, the students would record them on a common sheet, arranging them in a logical order. Thus, knowledge of phraseological units would deepen, children would learn to work with information, highlighting the necessary and discarding the secondary, the formation of skills of educational cooperation would continue, i.e. students learned to learn.

Functional literacy, in addition to the ability to learn, also implies a tolerant, respectful attitude towards other peoples and their cultures. We believe that one of the conditions for the formation of a functionally literate linguistic personality is the ability to build a dialogue of cultures that allows you to have a conversation with society. This means that a person is able to understand the views of representatives of different cultures, times and ages, distinguishing between his own and others' points of view; refer to texts of a different culture when solving educational problems; treat with understanding a different image of the world in the works of a different culture.

In order to form a respectful attitude towards the languages of other peoples, children would be asked to look for phraseological units in other languages, compare them with stable expressions of the Russian language. So, it is possible to organize work to search for phraseological units in the languages of the peoples inhabiting our country, or to turn to the languages of the peoples living in the neighborhood of Russia. First of all, we would turn to the national composition of the class, and also explore the language that children learn in foreign language lessons (English).

Phraseological units from different languages would be compared, as a result of which the children would come to the idea of the originality of the phraseology of each language, that it reflects values, ideals, people's ideas about the world, about their lives. Thus, the attitude towards the language as a cultural value is formed.

When studying the role of phraseological units in the Russian language, linguistic observation and a linguistic experiment would be used. For example, students would be given the task at home to pick up works of art in which phraseological units are found. Further, in one of the laboratory classes in these works, schoolchildren would find, underline and write out phraseological units, explaining their meanings, replacing set expressions with ordinary words and comparing the resulting texts.

Original text

Once I was with him on a short leg. But one day he (he got up on his left foot, or what?) Climbed to me to fight. I'm home with all my legs! Barely took his legs! But now not a foot to him. He won't have my leg anymore!

Changed text

Once I was friends with him. But one day he (was in a bad mood, or what?) Started to fight with me. I quickly ran home! Escaped with difficulty! But now I don't go to him. And I will never visit him again!

Students conclude that phraseological units are needed for the expressiveness of speech, its figurativeness, brightness and accuracy.

Phraseologisms are often used in folk tales and children's poems.

Here are some examples:

They say mom

Hands are not simple.

They say mom

Golden hands.

I'll look carefully

I'll take a closer look.

I stroke my mother's hands

I don't see gold.

(M. Rodina)

Early in the morning mama

I sent my son to class.

She said: "Don't fight

Don't tease, don't tease

Hurry up, it's time.

Well, no fluff or feathers!"

An hour later, barely alive,

The rooster goes home.

Barely hobbles

He's from the schoolyard

And on it, in fact

There is no fluff or feather.

(V. Orlov)

Watching phraseological units in literary texts, younger students practice finding them, recognizing them, joining the culture, see examples of expressing emotions with the help of phraseological units.

The position in education "knowledge for the sake of knowledge" is a thing of the past. Its place is taken by another: knowledge must be able to apply in life to solve practical problems. This means that research work provides for the presence of not only a theoretical, but also a practical part, experimentation, and the use of knowledge in practice.

You can offer children a variety of creative tasks:

- compose a story or a fairy tale using phraseological units you like;
- make drawings that reflect the direct meaning of phraseological units;
- compose and solve a crossword puzzle; write a report, take an interview;
- come up with a fantasy story or a mystical thriller.

As an example, we can cite the story that was composed by the third grader Daniel K.: Ivan, who does not remember kinship

There lived a boy. His parents loved and cared for him very much. The boy loved to play hockey. When he grew up, he did not want to bury his talent in the ground and left with the team for another city.

Parents missed the boy very much, and he kept putting off the trip home. He behaved like a two-faced Janus: in telephone conversations he kept promising to come, but he did not keep his promises.

Probably, the boy thought only of himself and did not care about his parents. After all, you do not need to be seven spans in the forehead to remember your loved ones.

Based on the analysis and generalization of the conducted educational and research work, the students, together with the teacher, formulate conclusions. In the course of work, students begin to understand and perceive phraseological units as a manifestation of the richness of the Russian language. They come to the realization that set expressions enrich our speech, make it figurative, vivid, emotional and include phraseological units in their speech. In addition, children learn to write scientific articles and reports, speak with them, and publish them in a school magazine.

At the end of the session, we would conduct an analysis and self-assessment of our own activities in terms of the personal contribution of each participant to the work done, if this is a collective activity, and in terms of personal significance in individual work.

Thus, through the organization of educational and research activities outside school hours, the following UUDs are formed in the Russian language for younger students:

- ability to goal-setting and planning;
- search and selection of relevant information and assimilation of the necessary language knowledge;
- practical application of school knowledge in various, including non-standard, situations;
- introspection and reflection;
- development of communicative competence.

All this contributes to the formation of a functionally literate language personality of a younger student and an increase in its level.

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